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**IMPACT OF SMALL AND MEDIUM SCALE BUILDING CONSTRUCTION ENTERPRISES ON
YOUTH EMPOWERMENT IN BAUCHI METROPOLIS OF BAUCHI STATE**

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Abstract

This study Assessed the Impact of Small and Medium Scale Building Construction Enterprises on Youth Empowerment in Bauchi Metropolis of Bauchi State. Based on the aim and objectives of the study, two research questions were raised and one null hypothesis formulated. Relevant literature related to the objectives and research questions were reviewed. The research design adopted for the study was a survey research design and the study covered all the registered block industries and quarry industries in Bauchi Metropolis of Bauchi State. The population of the study consist of 220 block industries and 15 quarry industries in Bauchi Metropolis of Bauchi State. The instrument for data collection in this study was a structured questionnaire. The instrument was validated by two experts from Building Technology Education of the Department of Vocational and Technology Education, Faculty of Technology Education, Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University, Bauchi Bauchi State. The data collected were analysed using IBM SPSS version 21 and the statistical tools used were mean and standard deviation: and it was discovered that the block and quarry industries in Bauchi Metropolis of Bauchi State have great impact on Youth Empowerment. The researcher therefore recommend that block and quarry industries should be empowered financially and otherwise in order to engage many youths with the intention of reducing problem of unemployment.

Keywords: Impact, Small and Medium Scale, Building Construction Enterprises, Youth Empowerment

Introduction

National growth and development of any country depends largely on the viability of entrepreneurial activities as well as contributions from both federal and state government to small and medium scale enterprises (SMEs). Building construction enterprises as embedded in SMEs can solve the problem of youth's empowerment in the areas of sales of building materials, production of building product and building services (Metu & Nwokoye, 2014). Developed and developing economies alike are fast driven by activities of SMEs at all levels and building block enterprises or industries play an important role. According to Ogbo and Agu (2014) small and medium size enterprises (SMEs) play a very significant role in national development and view SMEs as one of the major contributors of economic and social development in any country. Building construction enterprises and entrepreneurial development and operations across the globe are viable mechanisms and means of efficient economic progression. Building construction enterprises entrepreneurship will take its pride of place in quelling unemployment and thus generating employment among Nigerian youth's especially young graduates and place the economy on a proper footing.

SMEs in building construction enterprises if given the desired attention may serve as an important tool in youth empowerment for sustainable development of Bauchi State and Nigeria in general. The small and medium scale building construction enterprise is divided into classes such as, concrete blocks industry, interlocking industry, quarry industries, precast industry and marble industries.

Building construction can play a key role in small and Medium Scale Enterprises (SMEs) and are the backbone of economic development globally (Fagge, Galadima, Adepoju & Oladimaji 2022). Building construction SMEs plays a vibrant role in developed economies such as job creation, product innovation, research and development as well as employment and poverty reduction (Ahiawodzi & Adade, 2018). Building construction enterprises embedded in SMEs are recognized globally because of the role it plays in youth's empowerment and economic development. Agwu and Emetic (2017) defined SMEs as firms with investments in machinery and equipment not exceeding 500,000 naira and 2 million naira, respectively, with not more than 50 and 100 paid employees, respectively.

Building construction enterprises as part of SMEs is enhanced through gross domestic product (GDP). For instance, the construction industry account for about 5% in Nigeria GDP as compared to South Africa 19%, Mexico 17.7% and Ghana 8% (Usman et al. 2018). This is a clear indication that Nigeria is lagging behind in terms of youth's empowerment and economic development. Studies have shown that the Nigerian economy is dwindling especially in joblessness (Mailafiya, 2018). Evidently, 65% of Nigerian youths are unemployed (Usman & Keftin, 2019).

In the same way, United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO 2019) affirmed that about 92% of Nigerians survive on less than \$ 2 daily while about 71% survive on less than \$1 a day (Usman & Keftin, 2019). Furthermore, that 10 million Nigerians are living under poverty which constituted 62.5% out of 170 million. In addition, Nigeria is rated 158 out of 177 on Human Capital Development Index (Usman & Keftin, 2019). Issues that affect building construction enterprises SMEs in Nigeria that need redressed include economic situation, food and insecurity, politics amongst others.

Building construction enterprises as part of SMEs determined the GDP of a nation. For instance, in 2013, Nigerian GDP rose from \$262.6 billion US to \$510 billion (Mailafiya, 2018). In spite of Nigeria growth in GDP, it is still deficient in housing and improving livelihood (Usman *et al.*, 2018). In the same vein, SMEs accounts for 70% of Ghana GDP and 92% in South Africa and 70% of the manufacturing sector in Nigeria (Aigbavboa & Thwala, 2014). SMEs contribute more than 50% to the global economy and 95% of registered firms operating across the globe (Mag & Varothayam, 2015). This means that building construction SMEs are vital contributor of the economy. Therefore, building construction enterprises as part of SMEs are integral components of economic development, youth's empowerment and a key element in poverty reduction. According to World Economic Forum (2016), Building construction SMEs play an important role in youths' empowerment and economic development especially in developing countries by enhancing competition and entrepreneurship. The competition leads to innovation and skills development for construction SMEs. Turner *et al.* (2012) added that construction SMEs employ not less than 22% of adult population in developing countries. Berry *et al* (2017) buttressed that in South Africa, construction SMEs contributes 56% of private employment and 36% of GDP; and in Sierra Leone it employs 95% of the labour work force. This is a strong view of building construction SMEs influence in youth's empowerment and economic development through poverty reduction and is a clear indication that effort has to be intensified toward improved building construction enterprise as part of SMEs.

Building Construction enterprises as part of SMEs contributes greatly to job creation, social stability improves livelihood and reduce poverty. Building construction enterprises as embedded in SMEs add new products and services which invariably created employment opportunities, open foreign markets, increase market competition in the global market. In the same way, Construction SME's can account for most of the country's businesses, increased employment as well as improved the living standards of Nigerians and Bauchi in particular.

Statement of the Problem

Wide-spread of poverty and insecurity in Nigeria emanated from gross unemployment of youths which seems to threaten the realization of individual and societal socio-economic progress as well as the nation's sustainable development and nascent democracy. Youths in their numerical, energy, and creative strength are the most reliable change agents. Unemployment in any form globally propels youth restiveness, crime and associated vices and the attendant threats to nation building, peace and security (Bola, 2015)

Studies have shown that Small and Medium Scale Building Construction Enterprises have performed below expectation evident by high rate of unemployment and increase in poverty as well as lack of infrastructure for sustainable development (Usman, 2017). This has greatly affected the living standards of average Nigerians (Inuwa & Kunya, 2017). There are several issues that pose challenges to small and medium enterprises in Building Technology (block and quarry industries inclusive) such as technology, political, social and insecurity as well as high inflation rate which limit economic growth. However, effort geared towards making small and medium scale in building enterprises to meet up its requirement for economic and sustainable development proved to have failed. This study therefore, will seek to examine the Impact of Small and Medium Scale Building Construction Enterprises on Youth Empowerment in Bauchi Metropolis of Bauchi State.

Purpose of the Study

The aim of this study was to examine the impact of small and medium scale building construction enterprises on youth empowerment in Bauchi Metropolis of Bauchi State. The specific objectives for this study sought to:

1. Determine the impact of Block industries on Youth empowerment in Bauchi Metropolis of Bauchi State.
2. Determine the impact of quarry industries on youth empowerment in Bauchi Metropolis of Bauchi State.

Hypothesis

The study was guided by one null hypothesis tested 0.05 level of significance using t-test

H₀₁: There is no significant difference in the mean response of block industries and quarry industries on their impact on youth empowerment in Bauchi Metropolis of Bauchi State.

Methodology

The study used a survey research design and the area of the study was Bauchi Metropolis of Bauchi State. The population of the study consisted of 220 registered block industries and 15 registered quarry industries in Bauchi Metropolis of Bauchi State and total sample population was use. The instrument for data collection in this study was a structured questionnaire developed by the researcher titled a questionnaire for assessing the Impact of Small and Medium Scale Building Construction Enterprises on Youth Empowerment in Bauchi Metropolis of Bauchi State and the instrument was validated by

three experts and the instrument was subjected to reliability test using the cronbach Alpha. The reliability of the instrument was found to be .995 and the hence the instrument was found to be reliable. The rating scale for the instrument was highly impactful (5 points), impactful (4 points), Moderately Impactful (3 points), Not impactful (2 points) and seriously not impactful (1 point). The data was collected with help of trained research assistant and descriptive statistics mean and standard deviation was used to analysed the data was collected while t-test was used to test the hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance. The decision for this study is any mean score from 3.00 and above will be accepted as impactful while 2.99 and below will not be accepted. The decision rule for the hypothesis will be based on the confidence level of 0.05. if the p-value is greater than 0.05 the null hypothesis will be accepted and where otherwise will not be accepted.

Results and Discussion

Research Question One: What is the impact of block industries on youth empowerment in Bauchi Metropolis of Bauchi State?

Table 1: Mean and standard deviation of the respondents on impact of block industries on youth empowerment?

S/N	ITEMS	N	X	SD	Remarks
1.	Has the industry been impactful by helping youths secure jobs?	220	4.41	.713	Impactful
2.	Has the industry helped and impacted youths become responsible citizens?	220	4.27	.751	Impactful
3.	Has the industry impacted and helped youths to be independent?	220	4.05	.564	Impactful
4.	Has the industry being impactful by providing mentorship for young entrepreneurs	220	3.95	.826	Impactful
5.	Has construction SMEs been impactful in expanding the programme of imports substitution as well as the level of intermediate and capital goods production	220	4.57	.496	Impactful
6.	Construction SMEs has been impactful in initiating schemes designed to promote indigenous manpower development in industrial sector	220	4.08	.531	Impactful
7.	Has the industry been impactful by helping to raise the proportion of Construction SMEs indigenous ownership in the aggregate industrial investment in Bauchi	220	4.23	.719	Impactful
8.	Has the industry been impactful by helping engage youths meaningfully?	220	4.14	.758	Impactful
9.	Has the industry been impactful by helping reduced youth’s restiveness?	220	4.10	.896	Impactful
10.	Has the industry been impactful by helping youths to sustained themselves	220	3.95	.826	Impactful
	Grand Mean		4.17	.708	Impactful

Source: Fieldwork, 2023

Table 1 shows the Mean and Standard Deviation of the respondents on the impact of block industries on youth empowerment in Bauchi Metropolis of Bauchi State. The result shows that all the ten item questions are impactful with the mean that ranges from 3.95-4.57 and the standard deviation of .496-.896 respectively. The grand mean of the research question is 4.17 which means block industries in Bauchi Metropolis have great impact on Youth Empowerment.

Research question Two: what is the impact of quarry industries on youth empowerment in Bauchi Metropolis of Bauchi State?

Table 2: Mean and standard deviation of the respondents on the impact of quarry industries on youth empowerment in Bauchi Metropolis of Bauchi State.

N=15

S/N	ITEMS	X	SD	Remarks
21.	Has the industry been impactful by enabling youths to expand their business.	4.33	.488	Impactful
22.	Has the industry been impactful in training more youths	4.13	.640	Impactful
23.	Has the industry been impactful by enabling youths to acquire more tools which are necessary for training.	3.93	.594	Impactful
24.	Has the industry been impactful by giving youths the opportunity to acquire more equipment that is needed in executing the training.	3.73	.458	Impactful
25.	Has the industry been impactful by giving the opportunity to hire the services of consultants in different aspects.	4.67	.488	Impactful
26.	Has the industry been impactful in granting help in the smooth running of youth's business ventures.	5.00	.000	Impactful
27.	Has the industry been impactful in enabling youths to develop the business facilities to a very good standard.	4.27	.458	Impactful
28.	Has the industry been impactful in according to youths the opportunity to attain more training on youth empowerment in different places.	4.27	.594	Impactful
29.	The industry has been impactful in teaching youths how to operate tools and equipment's	4.27	.458	Impactful
30.	Has the industry been impactful in teaching youth's customer relationship	3.93	.704	Impactful
Grand Mean		4.25	.488	Impactful

Source: Fieldwork, 2023

Table 2 shows the Mean and Standard Deviation of the respondents on the impact of quarry industries on youth empowerment in Bauchi Metropolis of Bauchi State. The result shows that all the ten items are impactful with the mean scores ranging from 3.73-5.00 and the standard deviation of .000-.704 respectively. The grand mean of the research question is 4.25 and standard deviation .488 which mean quarry industries in Bauchi Metropolis have great impact on Youth Empowerment.

Null Hypothesis

There is no significance difference between the mean responses of block industries and quarry industries on their impact on youth empowerment in Bauchi metropolis of Bauchi State.

Table 3: t-test analysis of the mean responses of block industries and interlocking industries on their impact on Youth Empowerment in Bauchi metropolis of Bauchi State.

	N	X	S.D	Df	T	P	Decision
Block Industries	220	4.17	.708	234	-0.8	0.212	Accepted
Quarry Industries	15	4.25	.488				

The result of the independent t-test is presented in Table 6 showed that there is no significance difference between the mean responses of block industries and quarry industries on their impact on youth empowerment in Bauchi metropolis of Bauchi State within the df of 244, t-value = -0.8, p = .212. Since the p value is greater than the confidence level (P>0.05) therefore, the null hypothesis was accepted. This implied that there is no significance difference between the mean responses of block industries and interlocking industries on their impact on youth empowerment in Bauchi metropolis of Bauchi State.

Discussion of Findings

The finding of research question one shows that block industries have significant impact on Youth empowerment in Bauchi Metropolis of Bauchi State. This finding in line with that of Nimfa & Gajere (2017) who opined that Small Scale Enterprise block industries inclusive have great impact on youth empowerment thereby reducing the menace of youth unemployment. Furthermore, the finding agrees with that of Damiana, Abel, Christian, and Oluwaseun (2018) who also maintained that huge opportunities exist in the small-scale sandcrete block making industry in Nigeria. They further states that it is recommended that entrepreneurs and unemployed youths can consider the small-scale sandcrete block making industry as a means of engaging in profitable employment in Nigeria.

In the same vein the finding of research question two shows that quarry industries have significant impact on Youth empowerment in Bauchi Metropolis of Bauchi State. This finding is in agreement with that of Ukommi, Agha and Ekpenyong (2013) who also opined that quarry industry has significant impact on youth empowerment and has also helped in solving the problem of youth employment. This finding also agreed with that of Ugba and Targba (2021) who affirm that quarrying great help in poverty reduction among youths. In the same vein, this finding is also concord with that of Ishaya, Asokoro-ogaji and Ahmed (2023) who also opined that quarrying has socio-economic impact on the youth empowerment for sustainability in Kaduna State and beyond.

Conclusion

From the findings of this study, it shows that block industries and quarry industries and have significant impact on Youth empowerment in Bauchi Metropolis of Bauchi State thereby reducing the problem of unemployment which become a serious security threat to both life properties.

Recommendations

Based on the finding of this study, the researcher recommend as follows:

1. That all block industries should be empowered financially and otherwise in order to engage many youths with the intention of reducing problem of unemployment.
2. That all block quarry industries should be empowered financially and otherwise in order to engage many youths with the intention of reducing problem of unemployment.

References

- Agwu, M.O. & Emetic, C.I. (2017). Issues, Challenges and Prospects of Small and Medium Scale Enterprises (SMEs) in Port-Harcourt City. *European Journal of Sustainable Development*, 3(1), 101-114
- Aigbavboa, C. O. & Thwala, W. D. (2014). Challenges facing Black Owned Small and Medium Construction: A Case Study of Nelspruit - Mbombela Municipality, South Africa. *Journal of Economics and Behavioural Studies*, 6(10) 775 - 778.
- Ahiawodzi, A.K & Adade, T.C (2018). Access to credit and growth of small and medium scale Enterprises in the municipality of Ghana. *British Journal of Economic, finance and management Science*, 6(2) 34-51
- Anyadike, N., Emeh, I.E.J., & Ukah, F.O. (2012), "Entrepreneurship development and employment generation in Nigeria: Problems and prospects". *Universal Journal of Education and General Studies*, 1(4), 88-102.
- Berry, A., Von, B. M., Cassim, R., Kespor, A., Rajaratnam, B. |& Van, S. D. E. (2017). *Economics of SMME'S in South Africa, Trade and Policy Strategies*. Johannesburg, South Africa.
- Bola, A.B. (2015). Osun State Youth Empowerment Scheme: A Key to Sustainable Development. *Journal of Economics and Sustainable Development*, 6(9)260
- Damiana, A. A., Abel O. A., Christian, A. U., & OluwaseunA. A (2018). Opportunities in a Small-Scale Sandcrete Block making Industry in Nigeria: The Ingredients for Success. *International Journal of Research in Engineering and Technology* 07(09)
- Ugba D. & Targba A. (2021). Effect of small scale quarrying on poverty reduction among youths in Zamfara State, Nigeria. *Ancient of Journal of Agricultural Extension, Economics and Sociology*. 39(3), 75-84.
- Fagge A. M., Galadima S. A., Adepoju, S. A. & Oladimaji Y. U (2022). Socio-economic impact of participation in mining and quarrying on poverty alleviation among rural farming household in Kwara State, Nigeria. *Journal of Agriculture and environment*. Vol. 14 No:2(2022)/Articles
- Inuwa, I. I. & Kunya, S. U. (2015). Project Management Theory Exploration for Indigenous Contractors Project Planning in Nigeria. *International Journal of Engineering and Technology*, 60-72.
- Ishaya S. K., Asokoro-ogaji C. & Ahmed A. (2023). Socio-economic Impact of Quarrying in Kagarko Local Government Area of Kaduna State, Nigeria. Retrieve from [linkedin.com/pulse/soc](https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/soc)
- Metu, A.G., & Nwokoye, E.S. (2014), "Entrepreneurship development in Nigeria: Prospects and challenges", *International Conference on Entrepreneurship: Strategy for Socio-Economic advancement in Emerging Economies*, organized by the Department of Business Administration, Faculty of Social and Management Sciences, Bowen University Iwo, 28-30th May 2014.
- Mailafiya, O. (2015). Financing the Building Sector in Nigeria: Challenges and Opportunities. *Nigerian Building Industry and the National Economy: Synergies and Opportunities*, 2nd - 5th November, at The International Conference Centre Abuja, Nigeria (pp. 25 - 41). Abuja: Council of Registers Builders of Nigeria (CORBON).
- Mag, S. U. & Varothayam, V. (2015). An Investigation of Strategic factors affecting Performance of Manufacturing Based Small and Medium Enterprises in Sri Lanka. *2nd International Conference on National Capacity Building Strategy for Sustainable Development and Poverty Reduction*, 26th - 28th May, Dubai: American University of Emirate.
- Nimfa D. T., & Gajere M. C (2017). Small Scale Enterprises Innovation and Youths Empowerment for Local Economic Growth in Kanam L.G.A of Plateau State. *JOSR Journal of Business and Management(IOSR-JBM)* 19(10) 01-12

- Ogbo, A., & Agu, A.C. (2014), "The role of entrepreneurship in economic development: The Nigerian perspective", *European Journal of Business and Management*. 4(8).
- Usman, N. D. (2017). The Potentials of Life Circle Management for project Performance in the Building Industry in Abuja, Nigeria. Nairobi, Kenya: Unpublished PhD Thesis, Department of Environmental Planning and Management, School Environmental Studies, Kenyatta University
- Usman, N. D. & Keftin, N. A. (2019). Building Pathology and Sustainable Housing Delivery in Nigeria. African Regional Research Conference on Sustainable Development Strategies. Nairobi, Kenyatta University.
- Usman, N. D.; Inuwa, I. I.; Kolawole, R. O.; Kwari, J.M. & Didel, J.M. (2018). Evaluating the impact of housing delivery system on project performance within the building industry in Nigeria. *Journal of Environmental Sciences and Resource Management*, 135-145
- Turner, R., Ledwith, A., & Kelly, J. (2012, October 10th). *Project Management in Small and Medium Sized Enterprises: Tailoring the Practices to the Size of Company*. Retrieved from Business Enterprises: [http://www. ul.ie/business/sites](http://www.ul.ie/business/sites)
- Ukommi, A. S., Agha, E. O. & Ekpenyong, O. A. (2013). Industrial Development and Youth Unemployment: The Case of Crushed Rock Quarry Industry, Ishiagu in Ebonyi State. *Knowledge Review*, 28(2), 24-42